

An Equation Involving Cohesive Force for the Surface Pressure of Long Chain Ampholytes at Oil/Water Interface and Its Verification

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An equation for surface pressure, involving cohesive force, at oil/water interface has been derived for ampholytes and weak electrolytes. The equation has been tested with the experimental results obtained by Payens on monolayers of stearylphosphonic acid spread on oil/water interface and has been found to be fairly satisfactory.

Assuming stearylphosphonic acid to be an ampholyte its isoelectric point and the dissociation constant k_a have been evaluated from the data on surface pressure and area obtained by using different ionic strengths at pH 5.8. The pK_a and the pH corresponding to the isoelectric point have been found to be 4.66 and 3.73 respectively.

The origin of the cohesive force has been attributed to the dipolar character of the zwitter ions of stearylphosphonic acid.

In two previous papers^{1,2} some experimental evidence, available in the literature, on the existence of cohesive force between the CH_2 groups of long chain strong electrolytes at oil/water interface has been cited and an equation for the surface pressure of long chain ions taking this cohesive force into consideration has been formulated.

In the present paper the equation has been modified so as to suit ampholytes and its validity has been tested using the data on stearylphosphonic acid obtained by Payens^{3,4}. He has investigated the influence of pH and ionic strength on the surface pressure of monolayers of stearylphosphonic acid at petroleum ether/water interface. Considering the acid as a weak electrolyte he has modified the equation of Davies⁵ for long chain ions and has subjected the modified equation to test using his experimental results. It is found that the observed values of πA are much smaller than the corresponding values of πA calculated from the modified equation. He, therefore, assumed the existence of cohesive force between the long chain ions and molecules of stearylphosphonic acid at the oil/water interface. No attempt has, however, been made to account for this cohesive surface pressure quantitatively.

Derivation of the equation : From a critical analysis of the data recorded by Payens^{3,4}, we are led to the conclusion that stearylphosphonic acid is an ampholyte and that its isoelectric point lies between pH 2 and pH 5.8.

1. B. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 1120.
2. B. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**,
3. T. A. J. Payens, Doctorate thesis, University of Utrecht, 1955, 44.
4. T. A. J. Payens, 2nd International Cong. Surface activity, 1957, Vol. 1, 64.
5. J. T. Davis, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1951, **A208**, 224.

It is, therefore, assumed that at pH 5.8, $-(\alpha)^+$ and $(1-\alpha)^-$, represent the fraction of zwitter or dual ion and anion respectively and similarly at pH 2, $-(\alpha)^+$ and $(1-\alpha)^+$ represent the fraction of dual ion and cation respectively. According to Ghosh's¹ equation*, therefore, the contribution to the surface pressure made by the long chain anions is:—

$$(1-\alpha)n_0 kT \ln \left(\frac{A}{A-A_0} \right) + (1-\alpha)n_0 kT (\exp^{(A-A_0)a/A} - 1) \ln \left(\frac{A}{A-A_0} \right) - (1-\alpha) \frac{n_0 kT}{2} \ln f$$

that by the counter ions is; $(1-\alpha)n_0 kT \ln \left(\frac{A}{A-A_0} \right)$ and that by the dual ions assumed to behave as neutral molecules is; $(\alpha)n_0 kT \ln \left(\frac{A}{A-A_0} \right)$.

Hence, the total pressure observed, π , will be found by taking the algebraic sum of these individual contributions and that of the cohesive surface pressure $-\frac{a_s}{A^2}$ as proposed by Chatteraj and Chatterjee⁶.

Therefore, we may write;

$$\pi = 2(1-0.5\alpha)n_0 kT \ln \left(\frac{A}{A-A_0} \right) + (1-\alpha)n_0 kT (\exp^{(A-A_0)a/A} - 1) \ln \left(\frac{A}{A-A_0} \right) - \frac{(1-\alpha)5.8\sqrt{C}}{1+0.7\sqrt{C}} - \frac{a_s}{A^2} \quad \dots (1)$$

In equation (1) $n_0 = 1/A_0$ represents the adsorption when the surface is saturated, A , the area per long chain ion or molecule in (Angstrom)², a , has the values 0.93, 0.9 and 0.88 at the concentrations 1N, 0.1N and 0.01N NaCl respectively, $-5.8\sqrt{C}/(1+0.7\sqrt{C})$ has been substituted for $\frac{n_0 kT}{2} \ln f$ and a_s is the two dimensional Van der Waals constant. At substrate concentration $C = 0.001N$ or lower the term $(\exp^{(A-A_0)a/A} - 1)$ is replaced by $\left(\frac{A-A_0}{A} \right)$ only.

Distribution of the diffusible ions between the interface and the solution in bulk: On the alkaline side of the isoelectric point the fraction of the dual ion $-(\alpha)^+$ and that of the anion $(1-\alpha)^-$ will vary with pH. On the basis of Donnan's theory of membrane equilibria one may write that;

$$\frac{(\text{Na}^+)_s}{(\text{Na}^+)_b} = \frac{(\text{H}^+)_s}{(\text{H}^+)_b} \quad \dots (2)$$

* The equation is as follows:—

$$\pi = 2n_0 kT \ln \left(\frac{A}{A-A_0} \right) + (\exp^{(A-A_0)a/A} - 1)n_0 kT \ln \left(\frac{A}{A-A_0} \right) + \frac{n_0 kT}{2} \ln f.$$

where $(\text{Na}^+)_S$ and $(\text{H}^+)_S$ represent the activities of the Na^+ and H^+ ions at the interface and $(\text{Na}^+)_b$ and $(\text{H}^+)_b$ represent the activities of these ions in the bulk of the solution. It follows from equation (2) that at constant $(\text{H}^+)_b$ if $(\text{Na}^+)_b$ is increased then $(\text{Na}^+)_S$ will be increased and $(\text{H}^+)_S$ will be decreased i.e., the Na^+ ions will displace the H^+ ions from the interface. This will lead to a decrease in $-(\alpha)^+$ and an increase in $(1-\alpha)^-$ and a new equilibrium will be established.

In Table 1, for different pH and ionic strength, are recorded the values of $-(\alpha)^+$ and a_s which fit the equation (1) so as to make the calculated values of π (dynes/cm) agree with the observed values within the limits of experimental error. The experimental data at pH 5.8 have been taken mostly from Table 4 of Payen's³ thesis. The other data have been taken from Fig. 5 of his paper⁴. The value of A_0 used in equation (1) is 41 (\AA)² which is the same as has been used in the previous papers^{1,2}.

TABLE 1

pH	Concentration of NaCl	Percent $-(\alpha)^+$	a_s	A in (Angstrom) ²	50	100	150	200
5.5	1N	8	6,000	π Cal.	29.9	9.9	5.6	3.5
				π Obs.	29.3	10.6	5.4	3.8
5.8	0.1N	19	37,500	π Cal.	17.0	7.5	5.1	3.9
				π Obs.	16.9	8.0	4.8	3.6
5.8	0.01N	36	42,000	π Cal.	12.6	6.3	4.8	3.8
				π Obs.	12.2	6.4	4.6	3.7
5.8	0.001N	60	43,000	π Cal.	7.8	4.2	3.4	2.7
				π Obs.	8.2	4.4	3.1	2.5
5.8	Deionised water	80	33,000	π Cal.	7.8	3.7	2.8	2.3
				π Obs.	7.3	3.9	2.7	2.3
4.0	0.1N	84	26,000	π Cal.	9.3	3.8	2.8	
				π Obs.	8.8	4.3	3.1	
4.0	0	88	31,000	π Cal.	7.0	3.3	2.4	
				π Obs.	6.8	3.4	2.5	
2.0	0	56	40,000	π Cal.	9.5	4.8	3.7	
				π Obs.	9.8	5.0	3.4	

According to Payens at pH 5.8 for NaCl concentration of 1N, the experimental values of surface pressure, π_{obs} , show a scatter of 1 to 1.5 dynes, while for the lower concentrations the scatter is about 0.25 dynes. Taking this fact into consideration the agreement between the observed and the calculated values of π may be considered fairly satisfactory. It may be pointed out that at pH 5.8 as the NaCl concentration increases from 0.001N to 1N, $-(\alpha)^+$ decreases from 60% to 8% and consequently $(1-\alpha)^-$ increases from 40% to 92%. This variation is in agreement with the theory of membrane equilibrium discussed already.

It should also be pointed out that at pH 2 the observed values of π are greater than those at pH 4 with or without NaCl. If stearylphosphonic acid behaved simply as a weak acid then its degree of dissociation at pH 2 should have been much less than that at pH 4 and consequently π observed should have been smaller than that at pH 4. Since, just the opposite is the case, it may be reasonably concluded that stearylphosphonic acid is an ampholyte having its isoelectric point between pH 2 and pH 5.8.

The values of a_s at different ionic strengths cannot be compared quantitatively since a_s involves the thickness of the electrical double layer which varies with the ionic strength. Qualitatively, however, a_s appears to increase with the product $\alpha(1-\alpha)$. As the values of a_s are fairly high it may be concluded that the Van der Waal's type of attraction between the dual ions themselves and between the dual ions and the anions or the cations of the ampholyte, is quite considerable. Hence the generally accepted view that at oil/water interface cohesive force between the long chain ions or molecules does not exist is not quite correct.

Acidic and basic dissociation constants and the isoelectric point : According to Bjerrum's theory the basic and acidic dissociation constants and the isoelectric point of an ampholyte may be written as follows :—

or

$$\frac{(\text{H}^+)^-(\alpha)^+}{(1-\alpha)^+} = k_b \quad \dots (3)$$

and again

or

$$\frac{(\text{H}^+) (1-\alpha)^-}{-(\alpha)^+} = k_a \quad \dots (4)$$

where $-(\alpha)^+$, $(1-\alpha)^+$ and $(1-\alpha)^-$ represent the activities of the dual ion, cation and anion respectively and k_b and k_a are the dissociation constants.

Combining equation (3) and (4) the following equation for the isoelectric point where $(1-\alpha)^+ = (1-\alpha)^-$ is obtained

$$(\text{H}^+) = (k_b k_a)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (5)$$

The values of the dissociation constant k_b for some of the alkylphosphonic acids can be found from the literature. The values of the pK_b for methyl, ethyl and *n*-hexyl phosphonic acids as recorded by Kosolapoff⁷ are 2.35, 2.45 and 2.50 respectively. Therefore, considering the chain length of stearylphosphonic acid, the probable value of its pK_b may be taken as 2.8.

For the evaluation of the constant k_a the equation (4) may be used as follows :—

$$\frac{(1-\alpha)^-}{-(\alpha)^+} = \frac{k_a}{(\text{H}^+)_s} \quad \dots (6)$$

where $(\text{H}^+)_s$ refers to the activity of the (H^+) ions in the monolayer at the interface.

According to equation (2) we may substitute $\frac{(\text{Na})_s^+}{(\text{Na}^+)_b} (\text{H}^+)_b$ for $(\text{H}^+)_s$ in equation (6) and write as follows :

$$-\log \frac{-(\alpha)^+}{(1-\alpha)^-} = \log k_a - \log (\text{H}^+)_b - \log \frac{-(\text{Na})_s^+}{(\text{Na}^+)_b} \quad \dots (7)$$

At pH 5.8 the value of $\frac{-(\alpha)^+}{(1-\alpha)^-}$ for different values of $(\text{Na}^+)_b$ can be found from table I.

A plot of $P^{[-(\alpha)^+/(1-\alpha)^-]}$ against $P(Na^+)_b$ is found to be linear within the range investigated with a slope and intercept on $]P(Na^+)_b$ axis equal to 0.44 and 2.6 respectively. It is, therefore concluded that $(Na^+)_S = (Na^+)_b^{0.56}$ since the other terms in equation (7) are constants.

Substituting this value of $(Na^+)_S$ in equation (7) we find that when $P^{[-(\alpha)^+/(1-\alpha)^-]}$ is zero

$$\begin{aligned} -\log k_a &= P(H^+)_b - 0.44 \times 2.6 \quad \dots (8) \\ &= 5.8 - 1.14 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 1.

Hence $p^K a = 4.66$ approximately.

Substituting this value of $p^K a$ in equation (5) and taking 2.8 as the probable value of $p^K b$ of stearylphosphonic acid, the pH corresponding to the isoelectric point is found to be 3.73 approximately.

It may be mentioned that Payens^{3,4} has used 3.8 as the $p^K a$ of stearylphosphonic acid. It appears that what he has termed $p^K a$ is in all probability identical with $\frac{1}{2}(p^K a + p^K b)$ which is equal to the pH at the isoelectric point of stearylphosphonic acid.

The facts recorded above point to the conclusion that alkylphosphonic acids, specially the long chain ones, behave as ampholytes at oil/water interface.

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